

Knowledge, Attitude and practice towards Hepatitis B vaccination among medical and nursing students in South India

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Abstract

In spite of implementing regulated infection control practices and effective vaccination, hepatitis B infection remains a well-recognized occupational hazard among healthcare workers (HCWs). Most of the HCWs are not aware of the potential exposures to contaminated sources in the hospital environment and often do not seek post-exposure prophylactic management. By keeping this in mind, the present is designed to assess the knowledge, attitude, and practices among undergraduate medical and nursing students about hepatitis B infection and its vaccination. In this study, a total of 252 medical and 150 nursing students were recruited, and questionnaires related to knowledge about hepatitis B infection and vaccination, attitude towards infection and vaccination, and practices on infection control were included with 8, 8, and 4 questions, respectively. Most of the students involved in this study were aware of the hepatitis B infection. The overall level of knowledge of the respondents on hepatitis B infection and prevention was moderate. However, a significant proportion of the participants lack the requisite knowledge about post-exposure management. The study revealed a low level of hepatitis B vaccination coverage and a high rate of needle stick injuries. Further strategies for preventing workplace exposure, training programs on hepatitis B infection, including post-exposure prophylaxis, and increasing the vaccination coverage rate of all HCWs are highly recommended.

Keywords: Vaccination, Hepatitis B, Medical and Nursing students, KAP

Introduction

Infectious hepatitis exclusively affects millions of people globally, has a high mortality rate, and is still increasing over time, making it a global health priority. Among them, hepatitis B and C play a vital role in causing more chronicity, which leads to liver cirrhosis, cancer, etc., unreasonably defects, and lifelong infectious and carrier states (1). WHO has estimated 296, 58,

1.5, and 1.5 million people living with hepatitis B and C are infected with chronic hepatitis B and C, respectively (2).

Despite the implementation of best infection control practices and good medications to prevent liver damage and slow progression of the hepatitis infection, the utilization of effective vaccines helps to curtail the infection severity and spread. It is well defined that the hepatitis B infection is considered a major occupational risk among healthcare workers (HCWs) (3). Indian reports indicated that the receipt of booster vaccines against hepatitis B infection is scarce. It is noticed that a minimum number of paramedical professionals receive vaccinations when compared with doctors.

The HCWs have a four-fold greater probability of contracting hepatitis B compared with the general population, with a 6–30% risk of acquiring hepatitis B post-single exposure in an unvaccinated person (4,5), despite its preventable nature. Nearly 14.4% of hepatitis B infection rates are reported in HCWs, with the highest prevalence among dentists, nursing staff, dialysis unit staff, laboratory staff, or physicians (6). These HCWs are mostly unaware of their potential exposures to contaminated sources and often do not seek post-exposure prophylactic management (7). As far as overall hepatitis B prevalence among Indian HCWs is concerned, it reportedly ranges from 2.21% (1998) to 1% (2008) (8,9,10).

In this regard, the Government of India (GoI) has been taking many initiatives to prevent hepatitis B. It covers mandatory hepatitis B vaccination for under-five children under the Universal Immunization Programme (UIP), including timely birth doses, use of auto-disposable syringes for vaccination, safety of blood and blood products, and proper disposal of biomedical waste (BMW) (7). In June 2018, GoI further mandated compulsory vaccination for all HCWs under the National Viral Hepatitis Control Program (NVHCP) in coordination with UIP, who had not received a complete primary series before.

This involves the administration of a total of three hepatitis B doses within 1 to 6 months as per the adult hepatitis B immunization schedule. Other than conventional HCWs, NVHCP extends benefits to even those involved in conducting deliveries, giving injections, exposure to blood or blood products directly or indirectly, and so on (7).

Needless to say, today's students of health sciences (medical and nursing) are tomorrow's HCWs. Hence, they will be exposed to occupational risk for hepatitis B infection. In view of that, the stator bodies and the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare of India insisted on

hepatitis B vaccination for medical and nursing students at the beginning of their careers. Moreover, the medical and nursing students, when they get vaccinated, gain confidence and will become ambassadors for transmitting the message of hepatitis B vaccination and prevention to the community at large. Currently available systems do not ensure the completion of hepatitis B vaccination among medical and nursing students. As a result, the students tend to take a lean path and avoid completing vaccinations or do not get the hepatitis B vaccine. At this junction, it is possible that the hepatitis B vaccination can be completed with the support of their parents or guardians. Preventive studies also support the views of the student who does not get the hepatitis B vaccine or complete vaccination. Hence, the present study is proposed to find out the knowledge, attitude, and practice among the medical and nursing students.

Keeping the above background in mind, this study is designed to assess the knowledge, attitude, and practices among undergraduate medical and nursing students regarding hepatitis B and its vaccination.

Materials and Methods

This is a cross-sectional observational study carried out in the tertiary care teaching hospital in Tamil Nadu for a period of 3 months. All the first-year students admitted to B.Sc. Nursing and MBBS at five colleges were subjected to the study. The questionnaires were given to 800 students, but data collection was possible only for 252 medical and 150 nursing students.

The study was carried out after the approval of the institutional ethics committee (TSRMMCH&RC/ME-1/2021 Ref. No. 032, dated November 22, 2021). After informing study participants about the objectives of the study and ensuring the confidentiality of their data, written informed consent was obtained from all the participants.

The students' representative from the first-year medical and nursing students of the selected colleges was contacted by telephone, and a discussion was made in person with him or her. The importance of the proposal was explained, and we asked them to participate. The Google Sheet was used for the participation, and data were collected online since this was a questionnaire survey.

The medical and nursing students who were willing to participate were included, and the students who were denied or not willing during the day of the survey were excluded. The data were double-entried and analyzed using SPSS version 21.0; proportions of the KAP were

calculated and presented as frequencies (%); a p -value below 0.05 was considered statistically significant at a 95% confidence interval, and the adjusted odds ratios (AORs) were determined.

Results

Of the 252 medical and 150 nursing students sampled, all responded to the survey. Table 1 presents the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents. The majority of the respondents (71.4%) were female. 54.5% of them were aged \geq the median age of 23 years. 90.8% of them had never been married. The majority (71.4%) of them were first-year students. Only 41.3% of the parents or guardians of the students had attained tertiary education status.

Table 1: Sociodemographic details of the subjects included

Variables	Categories	Frequency (%)
Gender	Male	115 (28.6)
	Female	287 (71.4)
Age	< 23 years	183 (45.5)
	\geq 23 years	219 (54.5)
Marital status	Married	37 (9.2)
	Unmarried	365 (90.8)
Religion	Hindu	302 (75.1)
	Christian	32 (7.9)
	Islam	11 (2.8)
	No response	57 (14.2)
Residence	Rural	131 (32.6)
	Urban	271 (67.4)
Student	Medical	252 (62.7)
	Nursing	150 (37.3)

Knowledge, attitude and practice of hepatitis B infection prevention

The students' knowledge of hepatitis B infection prevention was analyzed. Aetiologically, only 41.0% of the students knew that hepatitis B infection is caused by a dsDNA virus. The respondents demonstrated varied knowledge of the following clinical manifestations of hepatitis B infection: infectiousness of hepatitis B infection carriers (75.9%), jaundice as a symptom of hepatitis B infection (59.7%), and not all infected persons becoming symptomatic (58.7%).

In terms of transmission, the nursing students recognized contaminated blood and products (90.8%), unsterilized surgical instruments (85.6%), unprotected sex (81.1%), and mother-to-child transmission (79.8%) as the major routes of transmission of hepatitis B infection. Also, 60.2% and 43.5% of the respondents knew that casual contact and the feco-oral route are not viable transmission routes for hepatitis B infection, respectively. The majority (53.0%) of the respondents knew the serological diagnostic method, while only 31.6% of them knew the polymerase chain reaction (PCR) diagnostic method. In terms of management, 76.6% of the students knew liver cancer was a complication of hepatitis B infection, and 61.9% of them knew that hepatitis B infection is incurable.

In terms of hepatitis B vaccination, only 28% of the respondents knew that hepatitis B vaccine is not derived from human blood. The majority (89.1%) of the students knew that the hepatitis B vaccine prevents hepatitis B infection. However, only 48.5% of them knew that the hepatitis B vaccine protects against liver cancer, and 54.0% of the respondents knew that post-exposure prophylaxis exists for accidental exposure to hepatitis B infection (Table 2).

Table 2: Knowledge about hepatitis B infection and transmission

No.	Questions/Statement	Frequency (%)	
		Yes	No
1.	Hepatitis B is a viral infection	165 (41)	237 (59)
2.	This infection causes liver disease	240 (59.7)	162 (40.3)
3.	Health care workers have an occupational risk for this infection	236 (58.7)	166 (41.3)
4.	Hepatitis B vaccine gives protection against Hepatitis B viral infection	305 (75.9)	97 (24.1)
5.	It is transmitted through needle stick injury (NSI)/sharp injury	175 (43.5)	227 (56.5)
6.	The infection can be transmitted by transfusion of infectious blood	365 (90.8)	37 (9.2)
7.	The infection can be transmitted by sexual intercourse	326 (81.1)	76 (18.9)
8.	The infection can be transmitted from infected mother to foetus	321 (79.8)	81 (20.1)

Table 3 displays the attitudes of the nursing students towards hepatitis B infection prevention. In terms of perceived susceptibility, 57.5% of the respondents perceived themselves to be generally at risk of hepatitis B infection, while 56.2% of them recognized that any exposure to blood is risky. The majority (87.8%) of them acknowledged that personal protective equipment usage is necessary during surgery. Regarding perceived severity or seriousness, the majority (87.6%) of the respondents acknowledged that hepatitis B infection is more serious than HIV infection. Also, 70.9% perceived aptly that hepatitis B infection is serious in terms of living a normal life. The majority (77.6%) of the respondents agreed that hepatitis B infection is serious regardless of its treatability. In respect of perceived threats, the majority of the respondents agreed that blood splashes (82.8%) and NSI (74.7%) should be reported.

Table 3: Attitude towards infection and vaccination

No.	Questions/Statement	Frequency (%)	
		Yes	No
1.	I do not bother about hepatitis B vaccination	231 (57.5)	171 (42.5)
2.	I feel that I am not exposed to patients directly at present	226 (56.2)	176 (43.8)
3.	I feel that I am healthy and I will not get hepatitis B infection	353 (87.8)	49 (12.2)
4..	I feel that I adopt adequate precaution	352 (87.6)	50 (12.4)
5.	My parents do not insist on my hepatitis B vaccination	285 (70.9)	117 (29.1)
6.	I do not want to waste money for hepatitis B vaccination	312 (77.6)	90 (22.4)
7.	If I get hepatitis B infection, there are medicines available for the infection	300 (74.7)	102 (25.4)
8.	I check for hepatitis B infection status of patients before examination	333 (82.8)	69 (17.2)

Table 4 suggests the students' practices or uptake of hepatitis B infection prevention activities. The prevalence of the practice of various hepatitis B infection prevention activities among the nursing students was reported as follows: hepatitis B screening (89.1%), changed gloves per client (84.1%), hepatitis B vaccination (72.1%), never splashed blood on the body (72.1%), never acquired NSI (70.9%), full dose vaccination (59.5%), never recapped needles (21.4%), and post-hepatitis B vaccination antibody testing (19.4%).

Table 4: Practice of hepatitis B infection prevention

No.	Questions/Statement	Frequency (%)	
		Yes	No
1.	I wear gloves while handling patients	358 (89.1)	44 (10.9)
2.	I will not handle patients if their hepatitis B status was not checked	290 (72.1)	112 (27.9)
3.	I wash hands thoroughly with soap after needle stick injury	78 (19.4)	212 (52.7)
4.	I take post exposure medicine if I get needle stick injury	97 (23.7)	313 (76.3)

Discussion

The overall level of knowledge of the respondents on hepatitis B infection prevention was moderate. This implies that the hepatitis B infection prevention education obtained by these students was inadequate. This inadequacy in respect of hepatitis B infection prevention education plausibly did not provide the enabling environment and capacity needed by the nursing students to exercise control over their own health. Poor control over their health arising from low knowledge is non-optimal for effective action towards disease prevention. Therefore, regular education on hepatitis B infection prevention, which has the desirable implication of promoting disease prevention, is crucial to the empowerment of these nursing students (11,12).

Our study also reported an overall moderate level of attitude among the respondents towards hepatitis B infection prevention. This finding of ours is similar to that in Cameroun. This moderate perception of the risk, severity, and threat of hepatitis B infection prevention by the nursing students implies that such students may be unwilling to develop personal skills relevant to hepatitis B disease prevention, even in the presence of a healthy hepatitis B infection

prevention policy and a supportive environment created through education and subsidized preventive healthcare services. A study even reported a poor overall attitude towards hepatitis B infection prevention among medical students. The differences in the findings of the various studies could be related to the nursing students' relative level of perception of risk, severity, and threat from hepatitis B infection, as well as the respondent's readiness to accept change as advanced by the five-stage cyclical transtheoretical model (13,14).

The overall practice of hepatitis B infection prevention was poor. Poor practice of hepatitis B infection prevention implies a lack of commitment to combating hepatitis B infection. Poor practices increase the student's exposure to the disease and their vulnerability to contracting and spreading the disease among their potential clients. This, therefore, necessitates advocacy for institution-based policies for regular practical skills training on hepatitis B infection prevention as well as compulsory hepatitis B screening, vaccination, and post-vaccination testing among all health trainees. These differences are plausibly related to the differences in the level of knowledge and attitude among the respondents and also to the social cognitive theory. The respondents intention to perform good practices in hepatitis B infection prevention is dependent on the triadic reciprocal determinism of behavior, attitude, and environment; observational learning; self-efficacy; and outcome expectancy. Therefore, the management of nursing training colleges should promote education on hepatitis B infection prevention as well as enforce proper professional conduct among the nursing students (15).

High knowledge of hepatitis B infection prevention was statistically significantly associated with an increased likelihood of exhibiting good practice in hepatitis B infection prevention, but only at the 10% significance level. This implies that the acquisition of adequate knowledge plausibly increases health consciousness, thereby enabling uptake of hepatitis B infection prevention activities such as avoiding NSI via the recapping of needles after use, among others. High knowledge of hepatitis B infection prevention enables nursing students to develop and sustain the requisite skills needed for hepatitis B infection prevention, which can empower them to exercise control over their own health (13,14).

A good attitude towards hepatitis B infection prevention was highly statistically significantly associated with a higher likelihood of demonstrating good practice in hepatitis B infection prevention. This means that a good attitude towards hepatitis B infection prevention, in the context of perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, and perceived threat, as proposed by

the health belief model, can directly influence the nursing students in respect of the performance of good practices in hepatitis B infection prevention. Additionally, the KAP-O framework proposes that attitude may interact with knowledge to produce the practice of hepatitis B infection prevention. Therefore, in promoting the health of nursing students, there is a need for trainee nurses to consciously adopt healthy attitudinal postures towards strengthening individual and community action for health promotion (15).

Being a male was also statistically significantly associated with an increased likelihood of exhibiting good practice in hepatitis B infection prevention. Therefore, male nursing students, in an attempt to remain relevant, are probably compelled to exhibit good practice in hepatitis B infection prevention, which culminates in effective hepatitis B infection prevention (13,14).

Married nursing students were statistically significantly more likely to demonstrate good practice in hepatitis B infection prevention. Marriage creates a sense of responsibility that compels people to be health conscious and, hence, to prioritize the promotion of the health and well-being of themselves and their families by taking up disease prevention activities, including hepatitis B infection prevention. However, we recommend that further studies be conducted to explore the detailed role marriage plays in promoting good practices in hepatitis B infection prevention (15).

Second-year nursing students were also statistically significantly associated with a higher likelihood of exhibiting good practice in hepatitis B infection prevention. This implies that long years of exposure to education and training confer the requisite knowledge and skills needed for adhering to good practices in hepatitis B infection prevention (15).

The tertiary education status of the students' parent or guardian was also found to be statistically significantly associated with an increased likelihood of performing good practices in hepatitis B infection prevention. This finding is explainable in the context of relative access to information and understanding of the importance of hepatitis B infection prevention. Plausibly, highly educated parents or guardians have greater access to and understanding of health issues like hepatitis B infection prevention from the media, including the internet. They are therefore significantly advantaged compared to their counterparts, who are unable to access the requisite information. Furthermore, highly educated parents plausibly take the initiative to locate and pay for hepatitis B infection preventive services such as hepatitis B screening, vaccination, and post-vaccination services for their wards (15).

In line with the findings of this study, several existing studies have also reported no statistically significant association between age, religion, program of study, and the practice of hepatitis B infection prevention. However, other studies have reported age, urban residential status, and name of college to be statistically significantly associated with good practices in hepatitis B infection prevention, although such associations were not statistically significant in our study.

To ensure the internal validity of the results, a standardized questionnaire was validated and tested for internal consistency. Recognizing the low response rate associated with online surveys, follow-up calls were made to ensure that many of the potential non-responders voluntarily completed the questionnaire. Respondents who had no access to data for internet connectivity were provided with hard copies of the questionnaire. Therefore, the response rate of 98.2% obtained in this study improved the external validity of our study. Finally, since our KAP survey relied on self-reported responses, the results of our study may not fully represent reality but the assumption of idealism.

Conclusion

Most of the students involved in this study were aware of HBV infection. However, a significant proportion of the participants lack the requisite knowledge about post-exposure management. The study revealed a low level of HBV vaccination coverage and a high rate of needle stick injuries. Further strategies for preventing workplace exposure, training programs on HBV infection, including post-exposure prophylaxis, and increasing the vaccination coverage rate of all HCWS are highly recommended.

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References

1. Gupta S, Gupta R, Joshi YK, Sarman S. Role of horizontal transmission in hepatitis B virus spread among household contacts in north India. *Intervirology* 2008;51:7-13.
2. WHO. Global progress report on HIV, viral hepatitis and sexually transmitted infections, 2021. [https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240027077external icon](https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240027077external%20icon).
3. Vipul MK, Rubee CT, Deepak NP, Chirag PP. Prevalence of hepatitis B virus infection in health care workers of a tertiary care hospital. *Nat J Med Res* 2012;2:176-178.
4. Byrne EB. Viral hepatitis: on occupational hazard of medical personnel. Experience of the Yale-New Haven hospital, 1952–1965. *JAMA* 1966;195:362-364.
5. Zeeshan M, Jabeen K, Anita NAA, Ailia WA, Saasia ZF, Vikram M, Afia Z. Evaluation of immune response to Hepatitis B vaccine in health care workers at a tertiary care hospital in Pakistan: An observational prospective study. *BMC Infect Dis.* 2007;7:120.
6. Polish LB, Tong MJ, Co RL, Coleman PJ, Alter MJ. Risk factors for hepatitis C virus infection among health care personnel in a community hospital. *Am J Infect Control* 1993;21:196-200.
7. GOI, editor. National Viral Hepatitis Control Program: Operational Guidelines. New Delhi: Ministry of Health and Family Welfare; 2018.
8. Elavia AJ, Banker DD. Hepatitis B virus infection in hospital personnel. *Natl Med J India* 1992;5:265-268.
9. Kumar KA, Baghal PK, Shukla CB, Jain MK. Prevalence of Hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg) among health care workers. *Ind J Comm Med* 2000;25:93-96.
10. Sukriti, Nirupma TP, Ankur S, Kireet A. Low levels of awareness, vaccine coverage, and the need for boosters among healthcare workers in tertiary care hospitals in India. *J Gastroenterol Hepatol* 2008;23:1710-1715.
11. Gebremeskel T, Beshah T, Tesfaye M, Beletew B, Mengesha A, Getie A. Assessment of knowledge and practice on hepatitis b infection prevention and associated factors among health science students in Woldia University, Northeast Ethiopia. *Adv Prevent Med* 2020;2020:9421964.
12. Almualm YK, Banafa NS, Al-Hanshi AS. Knowledge, Attitude and Practice (KAP) about Hepatitis B and C among Students of Hadhramout University, Al-Mukalla City, Yemen. *Acta Scient Med Sci* 2018;2:87-95.

13. Afihene MY, Duduyemi BM, A-Tetteh HL, Khatib M. Knowledge, attitude and practices concerning Hepatitis B infection, among healthcare workers in Bantama, Ghana: a cross sectional study. *Int J Comm Med Publ Hlth* 2015;2:244-253.
14. Zaeri AYA, Zaihi ZNR, AbuDyab FAM, Othman EEI, Somily EHH, Zalah AAA. Knowledge, attitude and practice among Jazan University students in health sciences colleges regarding Hepatitis B Virus and its vaccine. *Egypt J Hosp Med* 2018;73:6959-6966.
15. Rav-Marathe K, Wan THT, Marathe S. A systematic review on the KAP-o framework for diabetes education and research. *Med Res Arch.* 2016;4:1-21.
